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THE MONOTYPIC GENERA OF THE *BRASSICACEAE* BURNETT. FAMILY IN THE FLORA OF THE NAKHCIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

Aliyeva A.

ORCID: 0009-0009-8075-9490, Ph.D., Nakhchivan State University, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

МОНОТИПНЫЕ РОДЫ СЕМЕЙСТВА *BRASSICACEAE* BURNETT. В ФЛОРЕ НАКЧИВАНСКОЙ АВТОНОМНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ

Алиева А.М.

ORCID: 0009-0009-8075-9490, канд. биол. наук, Нахичеванский государственный университет, г.

Нахичевани, Азербайджан

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Abstract

The article discusses the monotypic genera of the Brassicaceae Burnett family in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. It highlights the position of monotypic genera in the flora and the importance of their conservation. A systematic review of these genera is provided, along with information on their biological, morphological, and ecological characteristics. The article also includes data on the elevation belts, ecological environment, phenophases, and life forms of the plants in question. Since most of the monotypic genera belong to the annual life form, characteristics specific to annual plants are also included here.

Аннотация

Статья посвящена монотипным родам семейства Brassicaceae Burnett в флоре Нахичеванской Автономной Республики. В ней рассматривается положение монотипных родов во флоре и важность их сохранения. Представлен систематический обзор этих родов, а также информация о их биологических, морфологических и экологических характеристиках. В статье приведены данные о высотных поясах, экологической среде, фенофазах и жизненных формах рассматриваемых растений. Поскольку большинство монотипных родов принадлежат к однолетним растениям, здесь также приведены характеристики, специфичные для однолетних растений.

Keywords: *Brassicaceae* Burnett., flora, monotypic genera, species, plant.

Ключевые слова: *Brassicaceae* Burnett., флора, монотипные роды, виды, растения.

The *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family is of great ecological and economic importance. This family, which has a wide global distribution, plays a significant role in food, medicine, and industry. The *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family includes over 3,000 species and more than 370 genera. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is known for its rich flora, and various representatives of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett family are found here. Plants of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family can thrive in various climates, but the unique climate of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic makes the distribution of these plants even more interesting. Although various species and genera of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family are present in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, monotypic genera are of particular interest. A monotypic genus is a genus that contains only one species, and this species is found endemically in a specific region. Such genera play a unique and distinct role in the ecosystem and are also of great importance in the conservation of biological diversity. In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, there are several notable examples among the monotypic genera of the family. These genera help maintain a specific ecosystem balance in certain environments with their species. The conservation of monotypic genera of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is crucial. These genera, represented by only one species, may face a

rapid risk of extinction due to natural disasters and human activities. Therefore, local flora conservation policies should focus on the protection of these genera. The management of both underground and surface resources, the preservation of the plants' natural habitats, and continued research on these genera can ensure their future. At the same time, research on these plants could help increase their use in modern industrial and medical fields. These genera are adapted to local conditions and are represented by a single species in certain geographical areas. The *Brassicaceae* (*Cruciferae* or mustard family) is a large plant family with approximately 338 genera and 3709 species distributed worldwide, most are distributed in the temperate areas of the Northern Hemisphere (Kawther Younes, et al. 2015). Numerous studies (e.g. Al-Shehbaz 1984, Price et al. 1994, Appel and Al-Shehbaz 2003, Koch et al. 2003a, Mitchell-Olds et al. 2005) have amply demonstrated that morphological characters in the *Brassicaceae* are highly homoplasious, making it virtually impossible to utilize them alone in establishing phylogenetic relationships on a family-wide basis or sometimes even within genera (Al-Shehbaz, I.A. et al. 2006). A distinctive and relatively rare feature of the *Brassicaceae* family is heterocarpy, which often develops simultaneously with heterospermy (Dorofeev, V.I. 2003). The *Brassicaceae* Burnett. is one of the leading families in the flora of the limestone formations in the southern Primorsk region,

the flora of the left bank of the Katun River, and the flora of the northern foothills of the Altai Mountains (Dudkin, R. V. 2004, Achimova, A. A. 2004, Zhikharova, O. N. 2004).

The *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family is represented by 67 genera in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Of these, 10 genera (14.92%) are monotypic:

Phylum: *Magnoliophyta*

Classis: *Angiospermae*

Subclassis: *Magnoliidae*

Superordo: *Myrtales*

Ordo: *Brassicales* Bromhead

Familia: *Brassicaceae* Burnett, nom. cons.

(= *Cruciferae* Juss., nom. cons.)

Genus: *Asperuginoides* Rauschert (*Buchingera* Boiss. & Hohen.)

Asperuginoides Rauschert (*Buchingera* Boiss. & Hohen.)

Genus: *Calepina* Adans.

Calepina irregularis (Asso) Thell.

Genus: *Coluteocarpus* Boiss.

Coluteocarpus vesicaria (L.) Holmboe

Genus: *Diptychocarpus* Trautv.

Diptychocarpus strictus (Fisch. ex Bieb.) Trautv.

Genus: *Euclidium* R.Br.

Euclidium syriacum (L.) R. Br.

Genus: *Leptaleum* DC.

Leptaleum filifolium (Willd.) DC.

Genus: *Litwinowia* Woronow

Litwinowia tenuissima (Pall.) Woronow ex Pavl.

Genus: *Myagrum* L.

Myagrum perfoliatum L.

Genus: *Nasturtium* R.Br.

Nasturtium officinale R. Br.

Genus: *Turritis* L.

Turritis glabra L. [*Arabis glabra* (L.) Brnh.]

***Asperuginoides* Rauschert (*Buchingera* Boiss. & Hohen.) (1849).** Plant annual, stem simple or branched from base, subflaccid, minute stellate hairy (Barish, B. and Nezaket, A. 2006). The cauline leaves are not pouch-shaped. The petals are undivided and white. The filaments of the stamens are simple. Short stamens have a small nectar gland on each side, and there is no middle stamen. The ovary is sessile, with a blunt, short, two-lobed style. The fruit is a round capsule that is flattened on the back, with branching veins and densely covered with hook-like hairs. The septum is weak, and the epidermal cells have walls with parallel divisions. The locules are one-seeded, but sometimes one locule does not develop, in which case the fruit becomes one-seeded. The seeds are of a simple shape with leathery wings. It is an annual plant with branched, hook-like hairs, and flowers are found at the axils (at the point where the leaf attaches to the stem) and are bent. It is an annual, xerophytic plant belonging to the Iran-Turan geographic element (Movsumova, F.G. 2005). It is spread in the broadleaf forests, dry, saline, rocky, and clayey areas of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Asperuginoides axillaris (Boiss. & Hohen.) Rauschert (*Buchingera axillaris* Boiss. & Hohen.)

***Calepina* Adans. (1763).** The stem branches from the base. The leaves are entire, serrated, with the lower leaves being lyrate or lyrate-pinnate, arranged in a rosette on long petioles. The stem leaves are elongated or elongated-lanceolate, sessile, with similar-shaped sharp auricles at their bases. The flower stalk is 6-16 mm long, spreading and becoming erect during fruiting. The sepals are separate, not pouch-shaped. The stamens are simple and free. The short stamen filaments have a serrated shape on the inner side, while the outer side has several concave nectar glands. In front of each long stamen pair, there is an elongated nectar gland. The ovary is sessile, and the style is very short. The small, reverse-ovate petals are white (Zeki, A., et al. 2020). Its fruit is small, ovate, leathery, indehiscent, with blunt, quadrangular ends, a net-veined husk, and the upper part narrows to a short tip. It is an annual plant with entire leaves and is hairless. It is an annual, mesophytic plant and belongs to the Eurasian geographic element. The genus is represented with *C. irregularis* (Asso) Thell. in Turkey, and we have not yet encountered any local usage or economic value of the species (Donmez, A.A. et al. 2020). It is spread in the grassy, low-moisture areas of the plains and foothill regions of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Calepina irregularis (Asso) Thell.

***Coluteocarpus* Boiss. (1842).** The sepals are flat. The petals are white or pink. The stamens are simple and free. The style is capitate. The fruit is swollen, thick, ellipsoidal or ovate, and is a capsule that opens at the apex. The husks are veined. The locules are 8-seeded, and the seeds are wingless. It is a perennial herb covered with simple hairs. It is a perennial, xerophytic plant and belongs to the geographic element of Anatolia. It is found in the dry and rocky slopes of the middle to high mountain ranges of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Coluteocarpus vesicaria (L.) Holmboe

***Diptychocarpus* Trautv. (1860).** The sepals are not net-shaped. The petal veins are purple. The ovary is sessile, with a short style and closely placed tubular parts. Short stamens have nectar glands on both sides. The capsule has two forms: the upper part opens, with compressed, wide-winged seeds, while the lower part is unopened, cylindrical, with narrow-winged seeds, and is divided into sections. The seeds are slightly compressed. These are branched, hairy, annual plants with elongated, veined leaves. It is an annual, xerophytic plant and belongs to the Iran-Turan geographic element (Kravchenko, A.V. 2007). It is found in the clayey, weakly saline slopes and grassy areas of the lower mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Diptychocarpus strictus (Fisch. ex Bieb.) Trautv.

***Euclidium* R.Br. (1812).** The sepals are spaced apart and are not net-shaped. The white petals narrow toward the base. The stamens are free and unific. Each short stamen has small, triangular nectar glands on both sides. The ovary is sessile, with a long, conical style. The fruit is ovate or ellipsoid, swollen, with two locules, an indeterminate covering, and numerous parallel walls. It is an indehiscent capsule. The beak is intersected, hook-shaped, and curved, with a single hanging

seed in each locule. These are annual, branched plants covered with simple hairs. It is an annual, xerophytic plant and belongs to the Eastern Mediterranean and Iran-Turan geographic elements. It is found in the semi-desert areas, along roadsides as a weed, and in fields up to the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Euclidium syriacum (L.) R. Br.

Leptaleum DC. (1821). The sepals are linear and flat. It has numerous small, whitish or whitish-purple petals. The long stamens pair up toward the apex. Each small stamen has one nectar gland on each side. The ovary is sessile, with a short style, and the stigma is a two-lobed, fused capitate structure. The fruit is linear, laterally compressed, difficult to open, leathery, with thick wings, a central vein, and small, reticulate lateral veins. The septum is spongy, with numerous epidermal cells having parallel walls. The seeds are elongated, small, and compressed, arranged in two rows. It is a dwarf annual herb with simple or pinnate leaves (Murat, Ü., Fevzi, Ö. 2007). It is a monotypic genus found in the Caucasus and Central Asia. It is an annual, xerophytic plant and belongs to the Iran-Turan geographic element. It is found in the dry, sandy, rocky slopes and clayey semi-deserts of the plains and foothill areas of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Leptaleum filifolium (Willd.) DC.

The species is listed as endangered in the flora of the Lower Volga Valley (Laktionov, A. P. 2004).

Litwinowia Woronow (1931). The sepals are flat, slightly pouch-shaped at the base. The petals are purple or whitish. The globe-ovate, indehiscent, glabrous capsule is 2-loculed, with two seeds, and easily disperses. The style is twice as long as the capsule. It is an annual plant covered with simple hairs. It belongs to a genus typical of open areas. It is an annual, xerophytic plant and belongs to the Turan geographic element (Ebel, A.L. et al. 2014). It is found in the dry slopes and grassy areas of the lower mountain range (often extending to the middle mountain range) of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Litwinowia tenuissima (Pall.) Woronow ex Pavl.

Myagrurum L. (1753). The stem is branched. The sepals are approximately 3 mm long, flat, with the sides slightly pouch-shaped at the base. The elongated petals, about 4 mm long, are yellow or pale yellow. The leaves

are entire, gray-green, with the lower ones being elongated, extending toward the flower stalk, usually fragmented and cut, blunt, triangular, while the upper ones are long, lanceolate, with a petiole surrounding the base, and have a pointed tip. The stamen filaments are unbranched. The ovary is sessile, with a triangular short style. The capsule is indehiscent, inverted pear-shaped, leathery, with two swollen, empty locules at the top, and a one-seeded, fruit-bearing locule at the bottom. The style is short and swollen. It is a hairless, annual plant. It is an annual, mesophytic plant and belongs to the European-Southwestern Asia geographic element. It is found in the cultivated areas and mainly in weedy places from the plains to the middle mountain range of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Myagrurum perfoliatum L.

Nasturtium R.Br. (1812). The sepals are identical, spaced, and bent. The elongated, inversely oval, petiolate petals are white in color (Zeki A. et al. 2020). The stamens are unbranched. Each short stamen has one large, outward-facing nectar gland, and there are no median glands. The ovary is sessile, and the style is visible. The fruit is short, cylindrical, swollen, and has a thick, smooth, leathery capsule with no veins. The septum is thin, and the epidermal cells are irregularly polygonal, slightly elongated, and have thin walls. The seeds are arranged in two rows in each locule. The seed capsules are flat, and it is a perennial aquatic plant. *Nasturtium officinale* a glabrous species or has a small hairs, unbranched unicellular, smooth sharp apex. (Post, 1933; Jafari and Hassand, 2012). Also the study Cumbus and Robinson (1977) confirmed that species *Nasturtium officinale* has two types of roots depending on environmental conditions. When there is a large amount of phosphorus in the water, the roots are adventitious, while the lack of phosphorus in the water, the roots are mainly Tap root. Formation of roots in water-cress helped it to widely spread in addition to the direct growth of the seed. (Sura S. A. et al. 2017). The genus includes only one species, which is distributed across almost all regions of the world. It is a cosmopolitan genus. It is a perennial, hydrophytic plant and belongs to the European geographic element. It is found in the wetlands and riverbanks of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, extending to the middle mountain range:

Nasturtium officinale R. Br.

The lenticular range of the species *Nasturtium officinale* R. Br. (Chalxanqala area, 17.05.2023).

***Turritis* L. (1753)** . *Turritis* was established in 1753 by Linnaeus, but most authors unite it with *Arabis*. (Al-Shehbaz, I.A., 2005; Mutlu, B. and Erik, S., 2015). Among the species that define the characteristics of the Volgograd-Stupinsk floristic region is *Turritis glabra* (Laktionov, A. P. 2004). The sepals are pouch-shaped at the base and stand upright. The elongated, linear petals are yellowish-white and have long petioles. The nectar glands are ring-shaped at the base of the short stamens, with the inner side slightly concave, and are connected to the wide median stamens. The sessile pistil has a very short style, and the stigma is capitate. The fruit is a linear capsule with clear central veins, with paired, flat, and membranous walls. The septum walls are thin, or thickened in the middle, and the epidermal cells are elongated with thickened walls.

The seeds are arranged in two rows in the locules. It is a branched, hairy biennial plant. It is a monotypic genus native to Europe, the Caucasus, Siberia, and Central Asia. The genus includes only one species, which is found in North America, Australia, Europe, and Asia. Its origin is believed to be Central Asia, but it has spread beyond its original range as a weed in agricultural fields. It is a biennial, xerophytic plant and belongs to the Palearctic geographic element (Kravchenko, A.V. 2007). The genus is found in the meadows, shrub edges, and roadsides of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, extending to the middle mountain range:

Turritis glabra L. [*Arabis glabra* (L.) Brnh.]

The species is listed as endangered in the flora of the Lower Volga Valley (Laktionov, A. P. 2004).

Research shows that the monotypic genera of the Brassicaceae Burnett family are represented by 7 annual, 2 perennial, and 1 biennial life forms. Among these plants, annual plants (7 species - 70%) are predominant. The fact that most of the monotypic genera are annuals can be explained by their short vegetative period. Annual plants can grow in various environments, including fields, gardens, and other ecosystems, because they possess characteristics that allow rapid reproduction and growth. Due to their very short life cycle, they have the ability to make genetic changes for the next generation. For example, species resistant to drought or cold can develop. Such plants respond specifically to arid climate conditions, which results in earlier flowering and fruiting phases. In the regional flora, the necessity for protecting annual plants arises due to the arid climate type of the area.

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